

The volatile constituents and key character impact compounds of two different commercial dark chocolates, each containing 64% of cocoa from different origins

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Abstract

The composition in flavouring substances and the sensorial profile of chocolate are known to be influenced by many parameters: the cocoa variety, the cocoa geographical origin, the cocoa fermentation and roasting conditions but also the chocolate recipe itself and its manufacturing. In this study, we analysed by SAFE-GC-MS/O (AEDA) two commercial dark chocolates, each containing 64% of cocoa from different origins: Peru and Costa Rica. While more than 10 components had a same and very high odour dilution factor respectively in both chocolates (e.g. vanillin, acetic acid, methional, furaneol, 2-phenylethyl acetate, 2-methoxyphenol), a higher impact of the 2/3-methylbutyl acetate and the delta-octalactone could be observed in the “Peru-chocolate”, explaining its typical fruitiness. The “Costa Rica-chocolate” with a more complex sensorial profile, reminiscent of olive, seemed for its part to be richer in 2,3,5-trimethylpyrazine, octanal and isovaleric acid to name a few.

Keywords: flavouring substance, aroma, sensorial characteristic, dark chocolate, cocoa origin

Introduction

The world of cocoa and chocolate is really fascinating. Today, by sharing their passion, knowledge and expertise, cocoa farmers and chocolate manufacturers or chocolatiers are able to offer a huge diversity of taste experiences to consumers, fulfilling their greatest need [1].

Many parameters are known to influence the final sensorial profile of chocolate: the variety of cocoa tree that is cultivated, the origin of this cocoa, the way the cocoa beans are fermented or roasted and the chocolate manufacturing processes that are applied. By combining and playing with these parameters, the possibilities to create something unique or characteristic are endless.

Obviously, chocolate is a very complex matrix, which contains hundreds of different flavouring substances. They all come indirectly from the ingredients that are used to make chocolate. Some of them or their precursors are generated by the yeasts and bacteria during the fermentation step of the cocoa beans. Others are issued from chemical reactions like the Maillard reactions during the roasting of these beans or from additional reactions during the conching of the chocolate itself, etc. Finally, along the way or over time, due to their high volatility or reactivity, some of these components also get lost or further transformed [1-3].

Because of this molecular complexity and the presence of fats or other foodstuffs, thorough and instrumental analyses of chocolate can be quite challenging and time-consuming. However, the most difficult part of this kind of studies very likely lies in making the links between these instrumental data and the consolidated input of a sensorial expert panel [4].

In this case, we analysed by the combined techniques solvent assisted flavour evaporation (SAFE) and gas chromatography-mass spectrometry/olfactometry (GC-MS/O) using the aroma extract dilution analysis (AEDA) olfactometric methodology two commercial dark chocolates, each containing 64% of cocoa from two different origins (Peru, Costa Rica) and we tried to correlate those results with their respective sensorial description.

Experimental

All the experiments were conducted separately by an external research institute (GC analyses) or a partner (sensorial analyses) and run as a proof of concept to determine which future investments would be the most relevant to make in our own analytical laboratory.

Extraction and concentration – SAFE + distillations

The extraction of the flavouring substances was done by putting 20 g (\pm 0.1 g) of dark chocolate in ~150 mL of dichloromethane (freshly distilled), stirring it all vigorously for 30 minutes at room temperature. The extract was then filtered and, afterwards, the volatiles were separated from the non-volatiles by means of the SAFE technique. The distillates were dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate, filtered, concentrated at 50 °C to ~3 mL using a Vigreux column and finally concentrated to ~100 μ L by micro-distillation.

Separation and identification – GC-O (AEDA) & GC-MS

The separation and sniffing of the flavouring substances via GC-O was performed using a TRACE GC (Thermo Fisher Scientific Inc., MA, United States) equipped with a DB-FFAP fused silica capillary column (30 m × 0.32 mm i.d., 0.25 µm film thickness). Aliquots (2 µl) of the SAFE-extract were injected manually by the cold on-column technique (40 °C). After 2 min, the temperature was raised at 8 °C/min to 235 °C (DB-FFAP), and held for 5 min. The flow rate of the carrier gas helium was 2.2 mL/min. At the end of the column, the effluent was split 1:1 by a Y-splitter. Two deactivated fused silica capillaries of the same length (30 cm × 0.32 mm i.d.) led either to a FID (250 °C) or to an Odour Detection Port (ODP, 250 °C). Linear retention indices (RIs) of the compounds were calculated by a homologous series of n-alkanes (C6–C26). AEDA with determination of flavour dilution (FD) factors was done by two trained panellists by diluting the distillate stepwise with dichloromethane (1+2 by volume). Each dilution step (1:3; 1:9; 1:27; 1:81; 1:243; v/v) was then analysed by GC-O. The highest dilution at which an odour of an individual compound was detectable was defined as the flavour dilution factor for that odorant. Detection in the undiluted extract corresponds to FD 1, detection in higher dilutions corresponds to higher FDs.

The separation and identification of the flavouring substances by GC-MS was performed using a GC-O/MS system consisted of a Thermo GC Ultra coupled to a DSQ II mass spectrometer (both: Thermo Fischer Scientific, Dreieich, Germany), equipped with the same capillary column as the one described above. Aliquots (2 µL) of the SAFE-extracts were injected at 40 °C using the cold on-column technique by a Multi-Purpose-Autosampler (Gerstel, Mülheim an der Ruhr, Germany), following the same temperature program than the one mentioned above. The flow rate of the carrier gas helium was 2.3 ml/min. Mass spectra were generated in the positive electron impact (EI) ionisation mode at 70 eV (scan 25-350 m/z).

Description – Sensorial analysis

The sensorial analyses (conventional profiling and quantitative descriptive analyses) were performed by seven expert panellists, exploiting the XLSTAT software.

Results and discussion

More than 65 different smells were detected by GC-O in these two dark chocolates. Those with the highest FD factors or with significantly different FD factors for each chocolate were identified based on their retention index, mass spectra, etc. (Table 1).

Dimethyl trisulphide, acetic acid, 2-ethyl-3,6-dimethylpyrazine, methional, 3-isobutyl-2-methoxypyrazine, 2-phenyl ethyl acetate, 2-methoxyphenol, ethyl-3-phenylpropionate, 2-phenylethanol, δ-octalactone, furaneol, γ-decalactone / ethyl cinnamate (co-eluting), (R)-5,6-dihydro-6-pentyl-2H-pyran-2-one and vanillin, commonly present in both analysed chocolates and characterised by FD factor ≥81, actively contribute to the overall sensorial profile of dark chocolate.

Table 1: The most odour-active or differentiating molecules in the two analysed dark chocolate extracts (1st part).

RI ^a	Flavouring substance ^b	Smell description ^c	FD factor ^d	
			Costa Rica	Peru
1121	2/3-methylbutyl acetate ^e	banana-like	1	27
1231	(Z)-4-heptenal ^e	fishy, cod liver oil-like	81	9
1275	octanal	citrus-like	81	9
1288	1-octen-3-one ^e	mushroom-like	243	27
1356	dimethyl trisulphide	sulphury, cabbage-like	243	243
1394	2,3,5-trimethylpyrazine	earthy	243	27
1427	acetic acid	vinegar-like	81	81
1433	2-ethyl-3,6-dimethylpyrazine ^e	earthy	81	81
1440	methional ^e	cooked potato-like	243	243
1500	3-isobutyl-2-methoxypyrazine	bell pepper-like	243	243
1636	2-methyl(3-methyldithio)furan ^f	fatty, broth-like	243	27
1657	2/3-isovaleric acid	sweaty	243	81
1664	2-acetyl pyrazine ^f	fatty, roasty	243	81

Table 1: The most odour-active or differentiating molecules in the two analysed dark chocolate extracts (2nd part).

RI ^a	Flavouring substance ^b	Smell description ^c	FD factor ^d	
			Costa Rica	Peru
1679	3-methyl-2,4-nonanedione ^f	sweaty, herbal	243	81
1785	2-phenyl ethyl acetate	flowery, rose-like	243	243
1842	2-methoxy phenol	ham-like	243	243
1858	ethyl-3-phenylpropionate	flowery	243	243
1883	2-phenylethanol	flowery, rose-like	243	243
1975	δ -octalactone	flowery, coconut-like	9	81
2017	4-hydroxy-2,5-dimethyl-3(2H)furanone (furanol) ^e	roasty, caramel-like	81	81
2100	γ -decalactone / ethyl cinnamate	coconut-like, cinnamon-like	243	243
2205	(R)-5,6-dihydro-6-pentyl-2H-pyran-2-one	peach/coconut-like	243	243
2530	vanillin	vanilla-like	243	243
2585	3-phenylpropanoic acid ^e	beeswax-like	243	81

^a Linear retention index (DB-FFAP) ; ^b Molecule identified based on its smell, retention index (DB-FFAP) and mass spectra (EI mode) ; ^c Smell perceived by GC-O ; ^d Flavour dilution factor determined by GC-O (AEDA) ; ^e No mass spectrum for this molecule ; ^f No mass spectrum for this molecule and no reference substance available to validate/check its RI

The higher impact of the 2/3-methylbutyl acetate in the “Peru-chocolate” correlates very well with the differentiating and subtle notes of banana spotted by the sensorial expert panel in this chocolate (Figure 1).

The “Costa Rica-chocolate” with its complex profile, described by the expert panel as more intense in hay and dried fruit notes (Figure 1) or by some of our chocolatiers as reminiscent of olives, has many molecules with a significantly higher FD factor than the one obtained for the same molecule in “Peru-chocolate”: (Z)-4-heptenal, octanal, 1-octen-3-one, 2,3,5-trimethylpyrazine, 2-methyl(3-methylthio)furan, 2/3-isovaleric acid, 2-acetyl pyrazine, 3-methyl-2,4-nonanedione, 3-phenylpropanoic acid.

Figure 1: Sensorial description of the “Costa Rica-chocolate” and “Peru-chocolate” with their respective and differentiating sensorial characteristics highlighted in blue.

Conclusion

It is nice to observe that the organoleptic impacts of the delta-octalactone and more especially of the 2/3-methylbutyl acetate, which are suspected to be higher in the “Peru-chocolate” based on the instrumental analyses and FD factors, are indeed very likely contributing to its typical and mild fruitiness.

The “Costa Rica-chocolate”, in which multiple and very diverse components like pyrazines, furans, organic acids and other carbonylated molecules seem to play a more discriminant role, has a different sensorial profile, which is also much more difficult or less straightforward to describe. Further and deeper analyses would be needed to highlight which molecules are the most critical and differentiating in this “Costa Rica-chocolate”. Nevertheless, thanks to these first and indicative results, the components to focus on in the future have been identified.

Finally, as an extra insight, please note that, with the same purpose, other instruments and methodologies (e.g. electronic nose or SPME(HS)-GC-O) were investigated in this study but the SAFE-GC-MS/O (AEDA) turned out to be the most appropriate and comprehensive approach.

References

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